

EVALUATION OF PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF HONEY IN ERER ZONE, SOMALI REGIONAL STATE, ETHIOPIA

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to evaluate the physicochemical properties of honey in Erer zone, Somali regional state. Thirty honey samples were analyzed for physicochemical properties. Honey samples were analyzed following the techniques proposed by the Quality and Standards Authority of Ethiopia (QSAE), European Union (EU), and Codex standards for honey. The physicochemical attributes evaluated were moisture content, ash, pH, acidity, hydroxyl methyl furfural (HMF), reducing sugars, and sucrose. The results obtained showed that overall average moisture content, ash, pH, acidity, HMF, reducing sugars, and sucrose were 18.42%, 0.23%, 4.07, 28.51 meq/kg, 23.46 mg/kg, 67.74 & 4.68, respectively, and there was no significant difference ($P>0.05$) in ash content, pH, and acidity between the two study locations. However, significant differences ($P<0.05$) in moisture content, HMF, reducing sugars, and sucrose were observed. In conclusion, the study indicates that the honey quality parameters examined in the two study locations meet both national and international standards, affirming that honey production in the Erer zone, Somali regional state, adheres to established quality criteria. Consequently, it is suggested that comprehensive investigations be conducted throughout the entire supply chain. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of conducting additional research on the nutritional and medicinal aspects of honey to facilitate accurate and targeted standardization processes.

Keywords: Honey quality, Physicochemical properties, Erer zone

INTRODUCTION

Honey is the most significant primary product of beekeeping from both quantitative and economic perspectives and the first bee product used by humankind in ancient times ([Geno, 2005](#)). Honey is a sweet and flavorful product that has been consumed as a food with high nutritional value ([Gomes et al., 2010](#)). It is a crucial commodity in the global market and is used for industrial purposes, as well as serving as a source of revenue for many nations ([CAC, 2001](#)). It is essentially composed of a complex mixture of carbohydrates, of which fructose and glucose account for nearly 85–95%, and other minor constituents, such as organic acids, amino acids, proteins, minerals, vitamins, and lipids ([Gomes et al., 2010](#)).

According to the [FAO \(2010\)](#), 45,300 metric tons of honey are produced per annum in Ethiopia, making the country the first honey producer in Africa and ninth in the world. However, most honey is crude and poorly managed. Honey is of good quality as long as it is in the hive, but faulty handling from the time of harvest until it reaches the market is responsible for its inferior quality ([Nuru, 2007](#)). Several factors have contributed to this low quality, among which high moisture content is a major quality problem in the country. Harvesting unripened honey, unsuitable honey storage containers, and storage places also contribute to a high moisture content

([Adgaba, 1991](#)). The quality of honey relies largely on the art of the producer in storing and blending the product. In honey marketing, consumers should be confident that they are getting good quality for what they are paying so that the country can earn foreign currency to revamp the national economy ([Geno, 2005](#)).

The composition and quality of honey, in general, are greatly influenced by geographical and environmental factors and the types of flowers utilized by bees ([Getachew et al., 2014](#)). Honey quality is mainly determined by its sensorial, chemical, physical, and microbiological characteristics ([Gomes et al., 2010](#)). The quality and properties of honey are also related to maturity, production methods, climatic conditions, processing and storage conditions, nectar sources of the honey, type of hive used, and the methods of collection and storage of honey ([Negeera, 2005](#); [Szczęśna et al., 2011](#); [Waś, 2011](#)).

Quality issues are the main concern for export commodities, and the volume of export honey in Ethiopia has declined over the last decade. This is due to deterioration in the quality of honey during harvesting, post-harvest handling, and marketing ([Beyene and David, 2007](#)). The quality of Ethiopian honey is generally poor, as a greater portion is harvested from traditional beehives (CSA, 2021). Faulty handling from the time of harvest until it reaches the market is responsible for its inferior quality. The type of hive used for harvesting and storing honey plays a vital role in determining its quality ([Beyene and Verschuur, 2014](#)).

Despite the large number of honeybee colonies and diverse honeybee floral resources, honey production is far below its potential in Ethiopia. This may be due to the fact that the apiculture sector has received little research and development attention, and because honey produced in the different agroecologies of the country has not been characterized to date. The physicochemical properties of honey produced at different geographical locations in Ethiopia have been reported by several researchers ([Gebremedhin et al., 2013](#); [Zábrodská and Vorlová, 2015](#)). However, in the Somali region in general and in the Erer zone, such primary information is lacking despite the potentiality of beekeeping and the production of large volumes of honey per annum. In the Erer zone, the majority of households keep bees and honey serves as a source of cash income for many households. Thus, to produce and improve the quality of honey that meets the demands of national and international markets and quality criteria, information about the quality of honey produced in the area is important. Therefore, the objective of this study was to evaluate the physicochemical properties of honey in the Erer Zone, Somali Region, Ethiopia.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the Study Area

This study was conducted in the Lagahida and Fik districts of the Erer Zone in the Somali Regional State, Ethiopia. Fik district lies at 8°10'N and 42°20'E. It is bordered to the south by Hamero, to the west by Qubi, to the west by Mayamuluka, to the north by the Jigjiga Zone, to the east by the Jarar Zone, and to the southeast by Sagag. The elevation of this woreda is 1035 meters above sea level. It had a temperature of 32 °C and 27% humidity. Lagahida district is bordered to the south by Salahad, to the west by the Oromia region, to the north by Mayamuluka, and to the east by the Erer, which separates it from Hamero.

Honey Sampling Procedure

A total of 30 samples (five from each location) (0.5-1 kg) were randomly collected from the beekeepers (producers). Honey samples were collected in a fresh, clean polyethylene bottle container and labeled with numbers, places, and dates of collection. The samples were prepared according to the [Codex Alimentarius Committee on Sugars \(2001\)](#). Each honey sample was analyzed separately for the selected physicochemical quality parameters.

Analysis of Physicochemical Properties of Honey

Analysis of the physicochemical properties of honey was performed at the Holeta Bee Research Center Laboratory. Honey samples were analyzed for moisture content (%), pH, total acidity (meq/kg), ash (%), HMF (mg/kg), sucrose (%), and reducing sugar (%). These parameters were analyzed following the methods of the [Codex Alimentarius Committee on Sugars \(2001\)](#), [European Union Directive \(EU\) \(2002\)](#), and [QSAE \(2005\)](#).

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SAS (version 9.2). The mean values were compared using the least significant difference (LSD) whenever ANOVA showed a statistically significant difference among means. The following statistical model was used.

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + A_i + e_{ij}$$

Where, Y_{ij} = response variable, μ = overall mean, A_i = effect of i^{th} location, and e_{ij} = random error

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physicochemical Properties of Honey

The results of the physicochemical property analysis of honey samples are summarized in Table 1. The results showed no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) in ash content, pH, or acidity between the samples obtained from the two areas. However, significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in moisture content, hydroxyl methyl furfural (HMF), reducing sugars, and apparent sucrose content were observed between the honey samples collected from the two locations.

Table 1: Physico-chemical properties of honey

Parameters	Lagahida	Fik	Overall	Pr>F
Moisture (%)	17.89±0.23 ^b	18.95±0.22 ^a	18.42±0.18	0.003
Ash (%)	0.24±0.11	0.22±0.12	0.23±0.08	0.17
HMF (mg/kg)	15.66±1.64 ^a	11.26±1.23 ^b	13.46±1.08	0.04
pH	4.13±0.08	4.02±0.07	4.07±0.05	0.33
Acidity (meq/kg)	26.73±1.53	30.29±1.58	28.51±1.13	0.11
Reducing sugar (%)	65.23±0.79 ^b	70.24±1.50 ^a	67.74±0.95	0.006
Apparent sucrose (%)	4.25±0.21	5.10±0.20	4.68±0.16	0.006

*Means followed by different superscripts within a row are significantly different ($P < 0.05$), HMF = hydroxyl methyl furfural

Moisture content

The mean moisture content of the honey samples was found 18.42% (Table 1). Water (moisture) content is one of the most pertinent characteristics of honey since it affects the thickness, specific weight, ripeness, crystallization, and taste of the honey, which enhances the shelf life of

the product at a certain value ([do Nascimento et al., 2015](#)). The overall mean moisture content of the honey samples (18.42%) was in the range of Ethiopian standards for Apis honey ([QSAE, 2005](#)) and international standard ([CAC, 2001](#)) moisture content for *A. mellifera* honey, which permits a maximum moisture content of 20%. Moisture content is the most essential quality component of honey, because the rate of fermentation, shelf life span, and processing characteristics are greatly influenced by the amount of moisture content ([Gebremedhin et al., 2013](#)). The moisture content of honey depends on the harvesting season, the degree of maturity that honey reaches in the hive, the type of hive used, environmental temperature, and moisture content of the original plant (Finola *et al.*, 2007; [Gobessa et al., 2012](#)). The moisture content of honey can be as low as 13% or as high as 23% depending on the source, climatic conditions, and other factors ([Bradbear, 2009](#)). High moisture content can accelerate crystallization in certain types of honey, increase its water activity to ferment, and deteriorate its quality ([Bradbear, 2009](#); [Gomes et al., 2010](#)).

Ash content

The average mean of Ash values obtained for honeys from the two locations was 0.23 (Table 1). The ash content indicates the abundance of mineral content in honey sources and constitutes a quality parameter that is mainly influenced by the nectar botanical origin, location, species of the bee, and processing and handling ([Marchini et al., 2007](#); [Biluca et al., 2016](#)). In this respect, [Biluca et al. \(2016\)](#) also indicated that the mineral content of honey depends on the nectar composition of major bee forages. In this study, it can be seen that honey from all the studied districts showed 0.23 mean ash percentage below the allowable maximum and thus conform to the international regulatory standards for quality honey ([QSAE, 2005](#)). This result is consistent with [Tesfaye et al. \(2016\)](#), who reported 0.14 – 0.3 the ash content of honey produced in Bale Natural Forest, Southeastern Ethiopia. Therefore, the results of the current study showed that the honey produced in the study area was floral honey, which is suitable for consumption and industrial purposes.

Total acidity

The overall average acidity of honey samples analysed in the present study was 28.51 meq/kg (Table 1), which is within an acceptable range in the world honey market ([CAC, 2001](#); [EU, 2001](#)). Differences in honey acidity could be caused by differences in geographical conditions, harvesting procedures, and storage conditions as well ([Kahraman et al., 2010](#)). Total acidity is also a quality parameter that corresponds to the presence of organic acids in honey that can influence honey fermentation ([Da Silva et al., 2016](#)).

pH

The overall average pH of honey in the study area was 4.07 (Table 1), and there was no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) between the study sites. This result agrees with the results of [Tesfaye et al. \(2016\)](#) and [Belie \(2009\)](#). Therefore, in the current result, the low pH of honey confirms that it well inhibits the presence and growth of microorganisms and makes honey compatible with many food products in terms of pH and acidity. All honeys are acidic, with a pH value generally lying between 3.5 and 5.5, due to the presence of organic acids that contribute to honey flavour and stability against microbial spoilage, as stated by [Adebiyi et al. \(2004\)](#). In addition, [Kinat \(2010\)](#) noted that this parameter has great significance during the extraction and storage of honey as it influences the texture, stability, and shelf life of the honey.

Hydroxy methyl furfural (HMF)

One of the most commonly monitored parameters for determining honey freshness and good practices by beekeepers is HMF ([Adebiyi et al., 2004](#); [Marchini et al., 2007](#)). The overall average HMF value of the honey samples analysed in the present study was 13.46 mg/kg (Table 1), which is within the acceptable range of world honey market standards. The average HMF value of Lagahida district (15.66 mg/kg) was significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher than that of Fik district (11.26 mg/kg). [Gomes et al. \(2010\)](#) and [Bogdanov \(2011\)](#) noted that the amount of HMF concentration increases with storage and prolonged heating of honey. Some countries set an HMF limit for imported honey (sometimes 40 mg/kg), and honey with an HMF higher than this limit will not be accepted.

Reducing sugar

The overall mean of reducing sugar in the honey samples studied was 67.74% (Table 1), which meets the quality standards of national and international limits. However, a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) was observed between the two locations. Similarly, [Tesfaye et al. \(2016\)](#) reported 66.4% reduction in sugar content of honey produced in Bale Natural Forest, Southeastern Ethiopia. The determination of sugars in honey is a quality criterion that is influenced by honey storage and heating and thus is an indicator of honey freshness and overheating.

Apparent sucrose

The overall mean of apparent sucrose was found to be 4.68 (Table 1), with a statistically significant difference ($P < 0.05$). The analysed results of the honey collected in this study showed that the average apparent sucrose of honey from Fik (5.10%) was significantly higher than that of honey from Lagahida (4.25%). The sucrose content of honey depends on botanical origin of nectar ([Gobessa et al., 2012](#)), its level should not exceed 5% according to an International Regulatory Standards. The result of this study reveals that sucrose content of honey samples from the study locations qualify the requirement of an International Regulatory Standards.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that overall average moisture content, ash, pH, acidity, HMF, reducing sugars, and sucrose were 18.42%, 0.23%, 4.07, 28.51 meq/kg, 23.46 mg/kg, 67.74, and 4.68, respectively. In conclusion, the study indicates that the honey quality parameters examined in the two study locations meet both national and international standards, affirming that honey production in the Erer zone, Somali regional state, adheres to established quality criteria. Consequently, it is suggested that comprehensive investigations be conducted throughout the entire supply chain. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the importance of conducting additional research on the nutritional and medicinal aspects of honey to facilitate accurate and targeted standardization processes.

Conflict of interests

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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